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Multifunctional structural energy storage composites

F. Huang^{1*}, Y. Zhou¹, S. Brown¹, A. N. Rider², and C. H. Wang¹

¹School of Mechanical and Manufacturing Engineering, University of New South Wales, Sydney, NSW 2052, Australia

² Aerospace Division, Defence Science and Technology Group, Melbourne, Victoria 3207, Australia.

*Corresponding Author (feng.huang@student.unsw.edu.au)

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Background

- Multifunctional structural energy storage devices, such as batteries and supercapacitors, have attracted keen interest owing to their potential for weight and volume reductions at system level and improved safety [1-3].
- One of the biggest challenges in this field is to maintain excellent (ideally the same as existing structure of the same weight) mechanical properties while storing adequate electrical energy. To this end, structural energy storage structures with both outstanding mechanical properties and electrical energy storage performance are highly desirable [4-8].

Project aims

- In this project, new structural concepts for composite batteries will be developed to store electrical energy, without sacrificing mechanical strength and stiffness. Examples include designing new energy storage cores for sandwich structures using either supercapacitor or laminated battery techniques.

Structural composite supercapacitors.

Fig.1 Carbon fibre-based honeycomb core structure supercapacitors.

Structural composite batteries

Fig.2 Carbon fibre-based sandwich structure batteries

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